

Jurisdiction of the International Court of Justice and Tribunals to Adjudicate the Great Ethiopian Renaissance Dam Dispute between Ethiopia and Egypt

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Abstract:

Ethiopia is the most populous landlocked country located in East Africa with the fastest growing economy in the world. Historical documents demonstrate Ethiopia's ambition to utilize the Nile River. Due to past financial constraints and volatile political instability, Ethiopia's long-awaited dam on the Nile River is finally being constructed. Ethiopia commenced the construction of the largest dam in Africa called Great Ethiopian Renaissance Dam (GERD) in 2011. Ethiopia's commencement of the GERD met strong opposition from Egypt and creates diplomatic strife between both countries. Egypt persistently invokes an exclusive historical right over the Nile River derived from colonial treaties. Ethiopia completed the GERD on September 2025 at the cost of 5 billion US dollars. Consequently, Egypt escalated the dispute to the United Nations Security Council because the GERD had been completed and commissioned without a consensus by Egypt and Ethiopia on the utilization of the River Nile. Besides this, during the 80th meeting of the United Nations General Assembly, Egypt emphasized its readiness to refer the issue of the GERD to international judicial bodies or arbitration, unless Ethiopia refrained from taking unilateral measures. This article examines the international legal frameworks that govern the situation and whether they bind Ethiopia to appear before the International Court of Justice or international tribunal to adjudicate the GERD dispute. This article takes the view that international law does not compel Ethiopia to appear before the court or international arbitration tribunals to defend its use of the Nile for the construction of the GERD.

Keywords: Nile River, GERD, International Law, Jurisdiction, International Court of Justice.

1. INTRODUCTION

The Nile is the longest river in the world, crossing eleven African riparian states.¹ Egypt exclusively uses the Nile River for centuries and it considers Nile as existential matter for Egyptian life.² In the past, Egypt attempted to control the source of the Nile River by waging war against Ethiopia in the 1870s.³ Although Ethiopia contributes 86 % of water to the Nile River does, Ethiopia did not utilize the Nile River until the commencement of the Great Ethiopian Renaissance Dam (GERD) in 2011.⁴ Egypt's diplomatic leverage over international financial institutions, aimed at prohibiting them from granting debt to Ethiopia for the utilization of the river, challenges Ethiopia's aspirations over the Nile River. Ethiopia's commencement of construction of GERD not only irked Egypt but it also disturbed its diplomatic relationship with Egypt and Sudan.⁵ Ethiopia's construction of GERD challenged Egypt's exclusive historical claims over the Nile River. Egypt saw GERD as a threat to its water security; nevertheless, the construction of a dam over the Nile River is considered by Ethiopia as an exercise of sovereign right.⁶

Various attempts have been made to reach an agreement between Ethiopia and Egypt on how both states can exercise their right over the Nile River. Egypt invokes colonial treaties to legitimize its ambition over the Nile River, while Ethiopia ignored these treaties on the ground that colonial treaties are contemporarily incompetent to create binding international obligations.⁷ Egypt wrote several letters to the United Nations Security Council which condemned Ethiopia's unilateral filling of water of the dam by treating GERD as a threat for international peace and security.⁸ As a result, the Security Council has met several times to deliberate over the GERD dispute. The Security Council recommends that the two states should resolve their water dispute under the

¹ Amin R. Yacoub and Becky Briggs, *The Right to the World's Longest River: Reopening the Vexing Case of the Nile River Case of the Nile River* (2022) 46 (2) *William and Mary Environmental Law and Policy Review* <<https://scholarship.law.wm.edu/wmelpr/vol46/iss2/4>> accessed on 17 October 2025

² Biong Kuol Deng, *Cooperation Between Egypt and Sudan over the Nile River Water: The Challenges of Duality* (2007) 11 (1) *African Sociological Review* 38

³ Ademnur Juhar, *Ethio-Egyptian Relations: Challenges and Opportunities* (Msc Thesis, Addis Abeba University 2003)

⁴ Amare K. Aweke, Mihrteab T. Taye and Yidnekachew M. Mekonnen, *The Grand Ethiopian Renaissance Dam: An Appraisal of Colonial Agreements, Issues of Existence and Forum for Negotiation* (2024) 1(1) *Ethiopian Journal of Strategic and International Affairs* 74

⁵ Francesca Caruso, *Ethiopia's Grand Renaissance Dam: The Law, History, Politics and Geopolitics behind Africa's Largest Hydropower Project* (2022) *The Istituto Affari Internazionali Paper*

⁶ Gashaw Ayferam Endaylalu, *The Grand Ethiopian Renaissance Dam (GERD): Geopolitical Implications* (2022) 5 *Ethiopian Journal of Water Science and Technology* 34

⁷ Dr. Thoko Kaim, *Colonial 'treaties' are not worth the paper unless expressly and freely adopted by the independent State* *African Legal Studies Blog* 20 December 2023 <<https://africanlegalstudies.blog/2023/10/20/colonial-treaties-are-not-worth-the-paper-unless-expressly-and-freely-adopted-by-the-independent-state/>> accessed on December 15, 2025

⁸ 'Analysis: Egypt's GERD complaint to the Security Council and its flawed legal arguments' *Addis Standard* (Addis Abeba, on 23 June 2020) <<https://addisstandard.com/analysis-egypts-gerd-complaint-to-the-security-council-and-its-flawed-legal-arguments/>> accessed on 20 October 2025

umbrella of the Africa Union.⁹ Consequently, Ethiopia expressed its commitment to resolve the GERD dispute under the auspices of the Africa Union.¹⁰ However, Egypt is reluctant to resolve the dispute as recommended by the Council; instead, Egypt appeals to the Security Council again and again. Egypt has said that it would use any measure to protect its exclusive historical right over the Nile River.

On 9 September 2025, Ethiopia officially inaugurated the completion of the GERD after fourteen years of construction. Egypt immediately wrote a letter to United Nation Security Council. That communication condemned Ethiopia's unilateral inauguration of the GERD in the absence of a binding agreement between two states.¹¹ Besides this, in the 80th meeting of the United Nations General, Egypt's Foreign Minister, Badr Abdelatty announced that 'Egypt is open to take the GERD dispute to the international judiciary and arbitration under international law'.¹² This article explores the binding international legal frameworks, particularly the International Court of Justice and tribunals, under which the GERD dispute may be adjudicated. This article is organized in to three sections. The first section presents the competing quest of Ethiopia and Egypt over the utilization of the Nile River. The second section addresses the jurisdiction of the International Court of Justice, and international tribunals to resolve the GERD dispute, and suggests three amicable solutions which may help to resolve the GERD dispute. The article ends with a concluding section.

2. EGYPT'S EXCLUSIVE HISTORICAL CLAIM OVER THE NILE RIVER AND ETHIOPIA'S OPPOSITION

The three colonial treaties which serve as the foundation for the claims by Egypt are discussed below.

2.1 The 1902 Boundary Treaty between Ethiopia and Great Britain

This agreement is primarily signed between Ethiopia and the United Kingdom to demarcate the boundary of Ethiopia and Sudan.¹³ However, this agreement contains some provisions over the utilization of the Nile River. As stated under article 3 of this agreement Ethiopia agrees 'not to construct any works on the Nile River, Lake Tana and

⁹ Reuters, 'U.N. Security Council backs AU bid to broker Ethiopia dam deal' accessed from <<https://www.reuters.com/world/un-security-council-backs-au-bid-broker-ethiopia-dam-deal-2021-07-08/>> accessed on 19 December 2025

¹⁰ Yonas Abiye, 'The GERD Dispute: A litmus test for 'African Solutions to African problems' *The Reporter* (Addis Abeba, 17 July 2021) <<https://www.thereporterethiopia.com/11691/>> accessed on 19 December 2025

¹¹ 'Egypt sends letter to UN Security Council over Ethiopia's unilateral GERD operation' *Ahram Online* (on 9 September 2025) <<https://english.alarabiya.net/News/middle-east/2025/09/09/egypt-protests-ethiopia-s-dam-inauguration-in-letter-to-un-security-council>> accessed on 20 October 2025

¹² Amr Mohamed Kandil, 'Ethiopia Deluded in Thinking Egypt will Forget its Nile Rights: FM' *Egypt Today* (Cairo, 27 September 2025) <<https://www.egypttoday.com/Article/1/142521/Ethiopia-deluded-in-thinking-Egypt-will-forget-its-Nile-rights>> accessed on 20 October 2025

¹³ Tadesse Kassa Woldetsadik, *Anglo-Ethiopian Treaty on the Nile and the Tana Dam Concessions: A Script in Legal History of Ethiopia's Diplomatic Confront (1900-1956)* (2014) 8 (2) *Mizan Law Review* 271 [Hear in After Tadesse Kassa]

Sobat, which arrests the flow of water except with the consent of Sudan and United Kingdom.’¹⁴ Egypt interprets this provision to mean that Ethiopia is under a legal obligation not to construct any dam over the Nile River without its consent.¹⁵ Accordingly, Egypt invokes this agreement to legitimize its exclusive historical claims over the Nile River.¹⁶ However, a careful interpretation of the agreement and contemporary rules and principles of international laws do not appear to support the position taken by Egypt.

Firstly, from the phrase “arrest” under article 3 of the agreement, we can infer that Ethiopia has agreed not to obstruct the full flow of the river to the lower riparian states through construction of dams on the Nile River.¹⁷ In this sense, Ethiopia can enjoy rights granted under international water law, so long as the construction of dam or the utilization of the Nile River does not completely block the flow of water to the lower riparian states.¹⁸ Secondly, this agreement is a conditional agreement. Article 4 of the agreement contains a phrase to the effect: ‘so long as Soudan is under Anglo-Egyptian government.’¹⁹ From this phrase, we can contend that the terms and conditions stipulated in the 1902 agreement are binding only as long as Soudan is under the colonial rule of Anglo-Egyptian government.²⁰ In this sense, rights and obligations embedded in the agreement are terminated upon the independence of Soudan. Sudan gained its independence in 1956.²¹ Therefore, the 1902 agreement lost its binding nature at the time when Sudan achieved its independence in 1956.

Thirdly, the agreement was not ratified by Ethiopia.²² Mere signing international treaties do not impose international obligations on states. Resultantly, so long as the agreement was not ratified by Ethiopia, the agreement lacks validity to impose obligation on Ethiopia.²³ Fourthly, the principle of Leonine treaty applies here: according to this international principle, treaties which accord rights to one of contracting parties alone are not binding. This principle has attained customary international law status. The terms of the 1902 agreement do not create any rights for Ethiopia, and thus, does not have a binding effect under international law.

¹⁴ Treaty between Great Britain and Ethiopia relative to the Frontiers between the Soudan, Ethiopia, and Eritrea (Great Britain-Ethiopia) (signed 15 May 1902) 192 CTS 469, art. 3 [Hear in after 1902 Agreement]

¹⁵ Aynalem D & Zerai A, Media’s portrayal of the Nile colonial treaties and its implications for the Grand Ethiopian Renaissance Dam disputes (2025) 21(3) Global Media and Communication 273

¹⁶ Ibid

¹⁷ Mohammed, Yusuf Ali. “The Endless Controversies of the Nile River Basin in The Context of International Trans boundary Watercourse Doctrines.” ASBÜ Hukuk Fakültesi Dergisi 4, no. 2 (2022): 895

¹⁸ Melat Assefa, ‘Negotiations on the Grand Ethiopian Renaissance Dam: Security Implications for Ethiopia ‘ (Msc, Addis Abeba University 2022)

¹⁹1902 Agreement art, 4

²⁰ Tadesse Kassa Woldetsadik, The Anglo-Ethiopian Treaty on the Nile and the Tana Dam Concessions: A Script in Legal History of Ethiopia’s Diplomatic Confront (1900-1956) (2014) 8(2) Mizan Law Review 271

²¹ Douglas Hamilton Johnson, ‘The Sudan under the British’ (1988) 29(3) The Journal of African History 541

²² Tadesse Kassa

²³ Tadesse Kassa

2.2 The 1929 and 1959 Agreement

The 1929 agreement was signed between Egypt and Britain (on behalf of Sudan) over the utilization of the Nile River.²⁴ This agreement contains several provisions which are inconsistent with water law principles which form part of customary international law, and the Convention on Non-Navigational Uses of International Watercourses.²⁵ Particularly, it denied the equitable utilization of natural resources. The agreement arbitrarily entitled the total annual share of the Nile River to Egypt in disregard of the rights of the upper riparian states.²⁶ The agreement awarded 48 and 4 billion cubic water for Egypt and Sudan respectively per a year.²⁷ Astoundingly, the agreement gives a discretionary power to decide over any projects and dams constructed by upper riparian states which reduces the water right of Sudan and Egypt.²⁸

Similarly, the 1959 agreement is signed between Egypt and Sudan for the full utilization of the Nile water, ignoring upper riparian states particularly Ethiopia which contributes 86% of the Nile River.²⁹ Two treaties denied the principle of equal and equitable utilization of natural resource that is recognized as a fundamental principle in contemporary international water law. International treaties can create obligations only on states that have signed and ratified the treaty, unless the agreement reaches the status of customary international law. Ethiopia is not a party to the two agreements, and consequently, there are no obligations which can be derived from them. Besides this, treaties signed during colonial era except boundary agreements do not create any rights and obligations. In conclusion, nowadays there are no rights and obligation which can be derived from the three colonial treaties.

²⁴ Joseph Kieyah & Daniel Kang, 'The Nile Agreement of 1929: Legal and Economic Analysis' (2012) Private Sector Development Division Kenya Institute for Public Policy Research and Analysis Working Paper No. 19

²⁵ Abiy Chelkeba, 'The Influence of the UN Watercourses Convention on the Development of the Nile River Basin Cooperative Framework Agreement (CFA)' (2018) 12(1) Mizan Law Review 165

²⁶ Edna Udobong, 'The Rising Conflict on the Nile Waters: Understanding its Legal, Environmental, and Public Health Consequences' (2016) 10(3) Liberty University Law Review 467

²⁷ Exchange of Notes between His Majesty's Government in the United Kingdom and the Egyptian Government in regard to the Use of the Waters of the River Nile for Irrigation Purposes (Egypt–United Kingdom) (signed 7 May 1929) 93 LNTS 43

²⁸ Dereje Zeleke, 'Between the Scylla of Water Security and Charybdis of Benefit Sharing: The Nile Basin Cooperative Framework Agreement-Failed or Just Teetering on the Brink' (2011) 3(1) Gottingen Journal of International Law 345

²⁹ Barbara Mielnik, 'The Impact of the 1959 Agreement on the Legal Status of the Nile in the Post-Colonial Period' (2021) 66(79) Studies in Logic, Grammar and Rhetoric 283

3. JURISDICTION OF THE INTERNATIONAL COURT OF JUSTICE AND INTERNATIONAL ARBITRATION TRIBUNALS TO ADJUDICATE THE GERD DISPUTE BETWEEN ETHIOPIA AND EGYPT

In this section, by examining existing international legal frameworks and principles, multilateral treaties signed by Nile River riparian states, and technical and scholastic arguments from academic literature, we will attempt to examine the jurisdiction of the International Court of Justice and international tribunals to adjudicate or arbitrate the water dispute arising from the Nile River between Ethiopia and Egypt.

3.1 Jurisdiction of International Court of Justice to adjudicate the GERD dispute

The International Court of Justice (ICJ) is the highest judicial organ of the United Nations.³⁰ The ICJ has exercised contentious jurisdiction and advisory jurisdiction.³¹ Contentious jurisdiction is the jurisdiction in which the ICJ adjudicates international disputes that arise among states.³² In this jurisdiction, only sovereign states are competent to bring a dispute before the ICJ. Therefore, international institutions, individuals and multinational companies cannot bring a dispute or be sued before the court.³³ Once the Court delivers a judgment on a contentious case, it's non-appealable, and binding on the parties involved.³⁴ A judgment rendered by the ICJ does not have precedent effect for states which are not party to the dispute.³⁵ Advisory jurisdiction is the jurisdiction in which the court provides a legal advice for organs of the United Nations, or international organizations on areas of international law.³⁶ Specialized Agencies of the United Nations can request advisory opinion from the ICJ on international legal matters that fall within their scope of activities upon the authorization of the United Nations General Assembly.³⁷ Unlike decisions given by the ICJ in contentious jurisdiction, opinions rendered by the ICJ in its advisory opinion are not binding.³⁸

³⁰ Tom Ginsburg, 'The Institutional Context of the International Court of Justice' (2021) Public Law and Legal Theory Working Paper Series, No.779

³¹ Ali Reza Annabi & Mahmoud Jalali, 'Study the Jurisdiction of International Court of Justice' (2021) 7(5) International Law Journal 19

³² Anastasia Telesetsky, 'Binding the United Nations: Compulsory Review of Disputes Involving UN International Responsibility before the International Court of Justice' (2012) 21(1) Minnesota Journal of International Law 314

³³ Christopher Greenwood, 'The Role of the International Court of Justice in the Global Community' (2011) 17(2) Davis Journal of International Law and Policy 233

³⁴ Kristen Walker, 'When can A Court Decision be Ignored: Critique and Comment' (2022) 46(2) Melbourne University Law Review 572

³⁵ Alexandra V. Huneeus, 'Compliance with International Court Judgments and Decisions' (2013) Legal Studies Research Paper Series Paper No. 1219

³⁶ Tillio Treves, 'Advisory Opinions of the International Court of Justice on Questions Raised by Other International Tribunals' (2000) 4 Max Planck Yearbook of United Nations Law 215

³⁷ Sir Kenneth Keith, 'The Advisory Jurisdiction of the International Court of Justice: Some Comparative Reflections' (1996) 4 Australian Year Book of International Law 39

³⁸ Attila Tanzi, 'Problems of Enforcement of Decisions of the International Court of Justice and the Law of the United Nations' (1996) 4 European Journal of International Law 539

International courts have no compulsory jurisdiction to adjudicate international disputes raised among the subjects of international law.³⁹ Instead, the jurisdiction of the court depends on the consent of disputants or parties to resolve their dispute before international courts.⁴⁰ Likewise, the ICJ assumes jurisdiction to settle international disputes that arise among states only when the parties to the dispute have consented to resolve the dispute before the court.⁴¹ States can express their consent in several ways. States can give their consent through signing a special agreement. When an international dispute arises, the disputing states may reach a one-time agreement (also known as a special agreement) to submit that specific dispute to the ICJ for adjudication.⁴² Moreover, states may sign treaties that include a jurisdictional clause stating that any future disagreement about the interpretation or application of the treaty may be brought before the International Court of Justice by any party.⁴³

Under Article 36, paragraph 2 of the ICJ Statute, a state may unilaterally declare that the Court has mandatory jurisdiction over all or particular types of legal disputes with any other state that has made a similar declaration.⁴⁴ The UN Secretary-General receives these declarations. There are several states which accepted the compulsory jurisdiction of the ICJ.⁴⁵ Egypt accepted the compulsory jurisdiction of the ICJ.⁴⁶ However, Ethiopia does not accept the compulsory jurisdiction of the ICJ. Moreover, there are no bilateral or multilateral treaties signed between Egypt and Ethiopia that empower the court to adjudicate disputes which arise from the utilization of the Nile River.

Besides, Ethiopia has not made a unilateral declaration to adjudicate international disputes before the ICJ. Accordingly, there is no international legal framework that obliges Ethiopia to appear before the ICJ, if Egypt brings the case of the GERD dispute before the court. More importantly, as stated under the 1997 United Nations Non-Navigable Uses of International Watercourses Convention, the International Court of Justice will assume jurisdiction to adjudicate disputes that arise from the interpretation and enforcement of the convention when the watercourse states consented for its compulsory jurisdiction at the time of ratifying, accepting, approving or acceding the

³⁹Anthony Giustini, 'Compulsory Adjudication in International Law: The Past, The Present, and Prospects for the Future' 1985 9(2) Fordham International Law Journal 213

⁴⁰ Bezaab Abebe Bahiru, 'Challenges of Dispute Settlement through International Court of Justice (ICJ): the Case of Ukraine v. Russian Federation the Decision on Provisional Measures on Alleged Violation of Genocide Convention' (2022) 18 (29) European Scientific Journal 64

⁴¹ Matthew Lister, 'The Legitimizing Role of Consent in International Law' (2011) 11(2) Chicago Journal of International Law 664

⁴²John Quigley, 'The United States Withdrawal from International Court of Justice Jurisdiction in Consular Cases: Reasons and Consequences' (2009) 19 Duke Journal of Comparative and International Law 263

⁴³ Terry K Smith, 'International Court of Justice -Jurisdiction -Resolutions to Expand the Jurisdiction of the International Court of Justice and to Improve the Court's Image as a Viable Alternative to Achieve Pacific Settlement of International Disputes' (1975) 5 Georgia Journal of International and Comparative Law 314

⁴⁴ Vanda Lamm, 'Declarations Accepting Compulsory Jurisdiction of the International Court of Justice' (2004) 45 (1) Acta Juridica Hungarica 25

⁴⁵ Declarations Recognizing as Compulsory the Jurisdiction of the International Court of Justice under article 36, paragraph 2, of the Statute of the Court, 15 October 1946 States parties having accepted the jurisdiction of the Court

⁴⁶ Ibid

convention. Ethiopia and Egypt do not ratify the convention and accept the jurisdiction of the court.⁴⁷ Therefore, Egypt's unilateral decision to take the GERD dispute to the ICJ does not empower the court to adjudicate dispute between two states. Consequently, there is no binding international legal instrument that binds Ethiopia to appear before the ICJ. On 23 March 2015 Ethiopia, Egypt and Sudan signed the agreement called "Agreement on Declaration of Principles."⁴⁸ This agreement contains an arbitration clause in its last provision.⁴⁹ In the agreement, the three states undertake to resolve disputes emanating from the interpretation and enforcement of the agreement through negotiation and consultation based on the principle of good faith.⁵⁰ Moreover, if states are unable to reach a settlement through negotiation, they may refer the dispute for mediation or reconciliation jointly, or submit the case for the head of state or government.⁵¹ Accordingly, some legal experts posit that this arbitration clause prevents Egypt from bringing a dispute before the International Court of Justice.⁵² However, others take the opposite position.

The Declaration of Principles is neither ratified by the signatories nor registered before the United Nation Secretary General. Therefore, the Declaration of Principles signed between the three states remain a gentleman's agreement, and does not create any rights and binding obligation on the signatories.⁵³ Nevertheless, some writers contend that unlike a memorandum of understanding, the Declaration of Principles uses the phrase "shall" in several of its provisions. Accordingly, they argued that Declaration of Principles creates binding obligation on the three states.⁵⁴ Under international law, mere signing a multilateral treaty or agreement does not create binding international obligation

⁴⁷ Convention on the Law of the Non-navigational Uses of International Watercourses 1997 Adopted by the General Assembly of the United Nations on 21 May 1997, Entered into force on 17 August 2014 art 33(10) [Hear in after 1997 water convention]

⁴⁸ Monica Moyo, 'Egypt, Sudan, and Ethiopia Sign Nile Dam Agreement' (March 23, 2015) American Society of International Law <<https://www.asil.org/blogs/egypt-sudan-and-ethiopia-sign-nile-dam-agreement-march-23-2015>> accessed on December 16, 2025

⁴⁹ Agreement on Declaration of Principles between The Arab Republic of Egypt, The Federal Democratic Republic of Ethiopia And The Republic of the Sudan On The Grand Ethiopian Renaissance Dam Project (GERDP) 23rd March 2015, Khartoum Sudan

⁵⁰ Jana Ayana, 'Negotiations on the GERD: Examination of the 2015 Agreement on the Declaration of Principle and Beyond' (LLM, Addis Abeba University 2021) 19

⁵¹ Saleh Salem, 'From the military option to the ICJ, how can Egypt respond to Ethiopia's GERD?' The New Arab <<https://www.newarab.com/news/military-option-icj-can-egypt-respond-ethiopia-gerd>> accessed on 16 December 2025

⁵² The New Arab, 'From the military option to the ICJ, how can Egypt respond to Ethiopia's GERD' <<https://www.newarab.com/news/military-option-icj-can-egypt-respond-ethiopia-gerd>> accessed on 19 December 2025

⁵³ Dejen Yemane Messele, 'Commentary: The 2015 Declaration of Principles is not a treaty and Ethiopia does not have obligations therefrom' *Addis Standard* (Addis Abeba, 21 May 2021) <<https://addisstandard.com/commentary-the-2015-declaration-of-principles-is-not-a-treaty-and-ethiopia-does-not-have-obligations-therefrom/>> accessed on 16 December 2025

⁵⁴ Ricarda E. von Meding, 'The Grand Ethiopian Renaissance Dam: A Large Scale Energy Project in Violation of International Law' (2022) 10(1) *LSU Journal of Energy Law & Resources* <https://digitalcommons.law.lsu.edu/jelr/vol10/iss1/6> accessed on 20 October 2025

on the signatories. Moreover, Professor Ayman Salama argued that the principle of good faith recognized in the Vienna Convention on the Law of Treaties makes the Declaration of Principles a binding international legal instrument on the three states.⁵⁵ Under the Ethiopian legal system, international agreements signed by Ethiopia create binding international obligation only when these agreements are ratified by the parliament and promulgated in the ratification proclamation.⁵⁶

Furthermore, states can invoke international agreements to legitimize or consolidate their argument and claims before the International Court of Justice only when such agreement are registered with the United Nations Secretary General.⁵⁷ International treaties signed by Egypt impose international obligation only when the signed treaties are ratified by parliament and published in the official gazette.⁵⁸ However, the Declaration of Principles is not ratified and published by Egypt. Consequently, the principle does not create any international rights and obligations on the signatories. Therefore, the principle does not deprive the International Court of Justice of jurisdiction over the GERD dispute between Ethiopia and Egypt.

3.2 Jurisdiction of international tribunals to adjudicate the GERD Dispute between Ethiopia and Egypt

Besides the International Court of Justice, the Foreign Minister of Egypt suggested during the 80th meeting of the UN General Assembly that Egypt will take the GERD dispute before international arbitration centers.⁵⁹ The Convention on the Law of the Non-Navigational Uses of International Watercourses (Water Convention) was adopted by the United Nations General Assembly in 1997.⁶⁰ The Water Convention codifies the pre-existing international customary laws.⁶¹ The UN Water Convention adopts two dispute settlement mechanisms which emanate from the utilization of Trans Boundary Rivers. Firstly, the convention adopted a preventive approach. The water convention tried to

⁵⁵ Noha El Tawil, 'Declaration of Principles on Renaissance Dam is Exclusive Agreement Binding Egypt, Ethiopia, Sudan Together: International Law Expert' *Egypt Today* (Cairo, on 23 June 2020) <<https://www.egypttoday.com/Article/1/88909/Declaration-of-Principles-on-Renaissance-Dam-is-exclusive-agreement-binding>> accessed on 20 October 2025

⁵⁶ Abebew Sisay Alemnow, Legal Effect of Unpublished International Law on Federal Negarit Gazette Under the Ethiopian Legal System (2025) 2(1) *Chokie Journal of Law* 55

⁵⁷ Megan Donaldson, 'The Survival of the Secret Treaty, Publicity, Secrecy and Legality in the International Order' (2017) 111 (3) *American Journal of International Law* 575,

⁵⁸ The Constitution of the Arab Republic of Egypt, 1971 (as Amended to 2007) article 151: It states that "*the treaties shall have the force of law after their conclusion, ratification and publication in accordance with the established procedure.*"

⁵⁹ Egypt's Foreign Minister says Ethiopia's Nile Dam Policy is Destabilizing Daily News Egypt (Cairo, on 28 September 2025) <<https://www.dailynewsegypt.com/2025/09/28/egypts-foreign-minister-says-ethiopias-nile-dam-policy-is-destabilising>> accessed on 20 October 2025

⁶⁰ Stephen C. McCaffrey & Mpazi Sinjela, 'The 1997 United Nations Convention on International Watercourses' (2008) 21 *Global Business and Development Law Journal* 165

⁶¹ International Union for Conservation of Nature, 'A window of opportunity for the Mekong Basin: The UN Watercourses Convention as a basis for cooperation: A legal analysis of how the UN Watercourses Convention complements the Mekong Agreement' 2016

prevent the emergence of water disputes by imposing precautionary obligation on the upper stream and lower stream states in the utilization of Trans Boundary Rivers.⁶² The convention imposed an obligation on watercourse states to exchange and provide accurate data and information to another watercourse state about the status of the watercourse; exchange measures taken on the watercourse, and “consult on the implementation of planned measures.”⁶³ Due their economic significance, Trans-Boundary Rivers are vulnerable to water disputes among riparian states. Resultantly, article 33 of the convention adopts a curative approach which is designed to settle existing water disputes among the watercourse states.⁶⁴ In this approach, there are two mechanisms which are recognized under the convention to settle disputes that arise from trans boundary rivers. The options are diplomatic (negotiation, mediation, consultation good office, joint watercourse institutions) and legal approach (arbitration and adjudication).

The Water Convention prescribes optional and compulsory water dispute settlement mechanisms.⁶⁵ As stated under article 33 of the Water Convention, states are required to redress water disputes that emanate from the interpretation of the convention through negotiations made in good faith.⁶⁶ Similarly, under the United Nation Charter, states are encouraged to resolve their disputes through negotiation and mediation.⁶⁷ The United Nation Security Council has recommend two states to resolve their dispute under the framework of the African Union. In the North Sea Continental Shelf case, the ICJ ruled that states in dispute have an international obligation to negotiate in good faith.⁶⁸ However, Egypt does not appear willing to negotiate with Ethiopia within the framework of the Africa Union. In addition, the convention emphasized the position that if the disputing parties are unable to reach a consensus, they may resolve their dispute through mediation, conciliation, a joint institution, or they may refer the dispute to an arbitral tribunal of the ICJ.⁶⁹ If the parties are unable to resolve their dispute through negotiation, they are obliged to submit the dispute to a Fact Finding Commission.⁷⁰ This is the only compulsory dispute settlement mechanism adopted in the Water Convention. Egypt has currently announced its readiness to bring the GERD dispute before international

⁶² Dinara Ziganshina, *The Role and Relevance of the 1997 UN Convention to the Countries of Central Asia and Afghanistan in the Aral Sea Basin* (Discussion Note, SIC ICWC/UNECE 2011) 11

⁶³ 1997 Water Convention art, 11

⁶⁴ 1997 Water Convention art, 33

⁶⁵ listair Rieu-Clarke and Flavia Rocha Loures, ‘Still Not in Force: Should States Support the 1997 UN Watercourses Convention?’ (2009) 18 *Review of European Community & International Environmental Law* 185

⁶⁶ 1997 Water Convention art, 33

⁶⁷ Charter of the United Nations (adopted 26 June 1945, entered into force 24 October 1945) 1 UNTS XVI art, 2 paragraph 1

⁶⁸ *North Sea Continental Shelf* (Federal Republic of Germany/Netherlands), 1969. ICJ. Available at <https://www.icj-cij.org/case/52> Accessed on 6th June 2025.

⁶⁹ 1997 Water Convention art, 33

⁷⁰ *International Law Commission, Draft articles on the Law of the Non-Navigational uses of International Watercourses and Commentaries thereto and Resolution on Trans boundary Confined Groundwater*, 1994

arbitration. However, this paper is of the view that the Water Convention does not allow Egypt to take the GERD dispute before international arbitration tribunals unilaterally. Invariably, the Water Convention does not impose an obligation on Ethiopia to appear before the tribunal on account of the following reasons:

Firstly, the Water Convention is neither signed nor ratified by Ethiopia and Egypt.⁷¹ Ethiopia did not sign the Water Convention because the convention does not protect the water rights of upper riparian states.⁷² Similarly, the convention is neither signed nor ratified by Egypt due to the reason that the convention provides privileges for the upstream riparian states.⁷³ As it is envisaged under article 36 of the convention, ‘the convention is to enter into force on the ninetieth day following the date of deposit of the thirty-fifth instrument of ratification, acceptance, approval or accession with the Secretary General of the United Nations’.⁷⁴ Accordingly, signatories become the party to the convention when they deposit their instrument of ratification before the UN Secretary General. However, both states did not ratify and deposit their instruments of ratification as required by the convention. In this sense, both Ethiopia and Egypt are not parties to the water convention. Therefore, in principle, the Water Convention does not impose an international obligation on Ethiopia and Egypt. Similarly, Egypt and Ethiopia cannot invoke the Water Convention to enjoy rights granted watercourse states under the convention.

However, the rules and principles which are codified in the Water Convention have attained customary international law status.⁷⁵ Therefore, so long as two states are not persistent objectors of the convention, the convention creates binding international obligation on Ethiopia and Egypt. Nevertheless, this paper is of the view that there is no evidence to demonstrate that the dispute settlement mechanisms envisaged in the Water Convention have attained customary international law status. Even if we contend that all provisions of the Water Convention have attained the status of customary international law, the two justifications pointed out prevent Egypt from taking the GERD dispute directly to international arbitration centres.

Secondly, the convention requires the establishment of a Fact-Finding Mission as a compulsory dispute settlement mechanism.⁷⁶ As stated under article 33(3) of the convention, states are compelled to refer disputes to the established fact-finding

⁷¹ Daniel Abebe, ‘Egypt, Ethiopia, and the Nile: The Economics of International Water Law’ (2024) 15 (1) Chicago Journal of International <<https://chicagounbound.uchicago.edu/cjil/vol15/iss1/4>> accessed on 20 October 2025

⁷² ‘United Nations General Assembly Press Release GA/9248’ International Water Law Project <https://www.internationalwaterlaw.org/documents/intldocs/convention_press.html> accessed on 20 October 2025

⁷³ Salman M.A. Salman, ‘The United Nations Watercourses Convention Ten Years Later: Why Has its Entry into Force Proven Difficult’ (2007) 32 (1) Water International 1

⁷⁴ 1997 Water Convention

⁷⁵ Ute Mager, *International Water Law: Global Developments and Regional Examples, Miscellanea Juridica Heidelbergensia* vol 3 (Jedermann-Verlag 2015)

⁷⁶ Ana Maria Daza-Clark, ‘Resolving Water Conflicts: Dispute Settlement Mechanisms Applicable to International Water Resources’ (PeaceRep Report: Climate & Natural Resources, University of Edinburgh 2020) 25

mission.⁷⁷ Therefore, the convention recognizes the doctrine of exhaustion of local remedies as a binding principle in adjudication of disputes that arise among states on the utilization of Trans Boundary Rivers. This principle precludes the disputing parties from taking the dispute before international courts and tribunals before exhausting all available remedies.⁷⁸ This doctrine primarily applies to disputes among individuals and states. The doctrine of exhaustion of local remedies is designed to protect the sovereignty of states by imposing an obligation on individuals to exhaust all available domestic remedies.⁷⁹ Accordingly, some authorities may contend that so long as the doctrine of the exhaustion of local remedies is not recognized as a rule of customary international law on inter-state disputes, states can directly refer the dispute to international courts and arbitration tribunals without first exhausting available remedies. Therefore, they may argue that Egypt can directly refer the case to international courts or tribunals without establishing a fact-finding mission. However, although the doctrine is primarily applicable to disputes that arise among individuals and states, the convention has crafted the establishment of independent fact-finding missions as a compulsory precondition.⁸⁰ As a result, we take the position that Water Convention recognizes the doctrine as a principle to resolve water disputes. Therefore, before attempting to bring the GERD dispute to the attention of international courts or tribunals, Egypt has to first request the establishment of an international autonomous fact-finding mission to investigate the adverse effect of the GERD over her water rights.

Thirdly, referring disputes on matters concerning the interpretation and enforcement of the convention to international arbitration tribunals, is an optional dispute settlement mechanism under the convention.⁸¹ Notwithstanding that the convention has adopted adjudication and arbitration as a final option to settle disputes emanating from the utilization of Trans Boundary Rivers, the convention does not oblige the states to appear before international courts and tribunals or arbitration centers.⁸² In this sense, states are not obliged to appear before the courts and tribunals to defend themselves, even when a suit has been instituted against them by another State. Moreover, as stated under the 1977 Water Convention, international arbitration tribunals assume jurisdiction to adjudicate disputes which arise from the interpretation and enforcement of the convention when the watercourse states consented for its compulsory jurisdiction at the time of ratifying, accepting, approving or acceding the convention.

⁷⁷ 1997 Water Convention art, 33(3)

⁷⁸ Divesh Kaul, 'A Functional Approach to Local Exhaustion of Remedies in International Law' (2025) 24(2) Washington University Global Studies Law Review 152

⁷⁹ Ibid

⁸⁰ UN-Water, UN-Water Policy Brief on the United Nations Global Water Conventions: Fostering Sustainable Development and Peace (UN-Water 2020) 16

⁸¹ Ram Prakash Anand, 'Enhancing the Acceptability of Compulsory Procedures of International Dispute Settlement' (2001) 5 Max Planck Yearbook of United Nations Law 1

⁸² Musa Mohammed Abseno, 'Role and relevance of the 1997 UN Watercourses Convention in resolving trans boundary water disputes in the Nile' (2013) 11(2) International Journal of River Basin Management

Ethiopia and Egypt do not ratify the convention and does not accept the jurisdiction of the tribunal.⁸³ Thus, Ethiopia is not obliged to appear before the court or international tribunals if Egypt decides to take the GERD dispute before international courts and tribunals.

This convention requires the establishment of a fact-finding commission as a mandatory mechanism to adjudicate water disputes among states.⁸⁴ Therefore, the Water Convention imposes an obligation on the disputing parties to resolve their dispute through negotiation, and a fact-finding mission. It is therefore a breach of the obligations in the Water Convention to escalate the dispute to a international tribunal or judicial body.

Another note of caution is the dilemma on the enforcement of the judgment of the ICJ, especially where one of the disputing parties decides not to abide by it. For instance, on 26 January 2024, the court ICJ ordered six “provisional measures” against Israel in its military operation in Gaza, in the case between South Africa and Israel.⁸⁵ However, Israel did not refrain from violating international humanitarian laws, and the measures ordered by the court. Israel continued to conduct military operations in Gaza.⁸⁶ Another factor to consider is that disputing parties before the ICJ cannot choose the applicable law used by the court in the adjudication process. The water dispute between Ethiopia and Egypt can be traced to the status colonial treaties. Both states interpreted colonial treaties in such a way as to suit their interests in the Nile River. As a result, the author suggests that the water dispute between the two states can be resolved in three ways. Firstly, by negotiation under the umbrella of the Africa Union.⁸⁷ Ethiopia has consistently expressed its willingness to resolve the water dispute through negotiation under the auspices of the Africa Union based on the principle of “equitable and reasonable utilization of natural resource.” However, Egypt prefers to refer to dispute to the United Nations Security Council. This paper is of the view that the parties should make a first attempt to resolve the dispute within the framework of the African Union. This will accord with the principle of “African solutions for African problems.” Indeed, reaching a consensus between Ethiopia and Egypt remains difficult as long as Egypt continues to pursue its historic claims over the Nile River from its interpretation of colonial treaties.⁸⁸

⁸³ 1997 Water Convention

⁸⁴ Ruth Lapidoth, ‘Dispute Settlement under the 1997 Convention on the Law of the Non Navigational Uses of International Watercourses’ (2000) 75 International Law Studies 231

⁸⁵ Gloria Fernández Arribas, ‘The ICJ Order on provisional measures of January 2024 in South Africa v. Israel on Genocide Case: An expected but disappointing decision’ (2024) 12 Euro Mediterranean Journal of International Law and International Relation 1

⁸⁶ Matthew Tentler, ‘Israel’s Non-implementation of the ICJ’s Provisional Measures: International Law Must Be Upheld’ Global Governance Institute (Brussels, 2 April 2024) <<https://www.globalgovernance.eu/publications/israels-non-implementation-of-the-icjs-provisional-measures-international-law-must-be-upheld>> accessed on 20 October 2025

⁸⁷ Wondemagegn Sisay Tefera, *The Role of the African Union in Resolution of the Great Ethiopian Renaissance Dam Dispute* (LLM Thesis, Addis Abeba University 2020)

⁸⁸ Tsegaye Shewangzaw Zergaw, *Mediated Negotiation over the Grand Ethiopian Renaissance Dam: Achievement, Challenges and Prospect* (2024) 1(7) International Journal of Water Management and Diplomacy

Another point is the need for Egypt to sign and ratify the Nile Basin Initiatives Cooperative Framework Agreement (CFA). The CFA recognizes ‘customary international water law principles, including the principle of equitable and reasonable utilization and the obligation to prevent significant harm.’⁸⁹ Moreover, this agreement ignored preferential rights over the Nile River and awards equal right of utilization for all upstream and downstream states. Therefore, CFA does not undermine Egypt’s water rights over the Nile River notwithstanding the fact that the agreement does not incorporate colonial treaties. However, Egypt is reluctant to sign the agreement because of the perception that the agreement challenges her historical rights over the Nile River.⁹⁰ So long as Egypt’s exclusive historical claim over the Nile River is challenged by Ethiopia through the construction of the GERD, and by initiatives by other riparian states, it will be impossible for only Egypt to utilize the Nile River. Therefore, practically Egypt cannot exercise exclusive historical right over the river even if it rejects the CFA. The position of this paper is that Egypt should sign the CFA to protect its water rights in accordance the law and principles enshrined in the CFA.

Another option is to conclude a binding bilateral agreement between Ethiopia and Egypt, which incorporates international water law principles. So far, the two states have been unable to reach a binding bilateral agreement on the settlement of disputes over the Nile River. There is a precedent here. The United States of America and Mexico successfully settled a water dispute by signing a binding bilateral treaty called “Water Treaty of 1944.”⁹¹ The position of this paper is for Egypt and Ethiopia to first, exhaust all possible diplomatic negotiation which available under the framework of the Africa Union or other regional organizations.

4. CONCLUSION

This paper has examined the legal issues involved in the construction of the GERD by Ethiopia over the Nile. This project challenges the hitherto, historical claim of Egypt on the exclusive use of the Nile River. This paper made several recommendations on the equitable use of the Nile by its riparian states, including exploring alternative dispute resolution methods within the auspices of regional arrangements. Negotiating in good faith is a recognized principle of international law. In addition, the United Nations Charter encourages states to settle international disputes through negotiation and mediation. Ethiopia repeatedly expressed its commitment to negotiate with Egypt within the ambit of contemporary international water law principles. However, Egypt has turned down diplomatic discourses with Ethiopia over the utilization of the Nile River.

⁸⁹ Mahemud Tekuya, Entry into Force of the Nile Basin Cooperative Framework Agreement: Challenges and Prospects, European Journal of International Law Blog (2 August 2024) <<https://www.ejiltalk.org/entry-into-force-of-the-nile-basin-cooperative-framework-agreement-challenges-and-prospects/>> accessed on 17 October 2025

⁹⁰ Scott O. McKenzie, Egypt’s Choice: From the Nile Basin Treaty to the Cooperative Framework Agreement, an International Legal Analysis (2012) 21 Transnational Law and Contemporary Problems 571

⁹¹ Kirsten J. Anderson, History and Interpretation of the Water Treaty of 1944 (1972) 12 (5) Natural Resource Journal 600